

DESIGN OF BUILDINGS IN SEISMICALLY HAZARDOUS AREAS

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Abstract. This research paper presents the accumulated scientific, theoretical and practical experience, analysis of earthquakes and other seismic events that have already occurred in our country and abroad, numerous and large-scale scientific research in the field of earthquake-resistant construction, modern design is carried out taking into account the basic principles.

Keywords: construction, design of buildings, seismic resistance, seismically hazardous areas.

Introduction.

The seismic resistance of a building primarily depends on its height, its weight as a whole, the structural system that takes on the seismic impact, the seismic regions where the object is being built, including micro seismic regionalization, since geological faults may exist in zones of low seismic activity, which may represent an increased geodynamic hazard of individual objects, especially high-rise buildings.

Traditional methods and means of protecting buildings and structures from seismic impacts include a large range of various measures aimed at increasing the bearing capacity of building structures, the design of which is carried out on the basis of standards and rules developed by domestic and foreign construction experience that guarantee the seismic resistance of buildings and structures in areas with seismicity 7, 8 and 9 points.

Methods of research.

The design of buildings and structures in seismically hazardous areas begins with the observance of the generally accepted principles of earthquake-resistant construction, according to which all building materials, structures and structural schemes used must ensure the lowest value of seismic loads. When designing, it is recommended to adopt, as a rule, symmetrical structural schemes and to achieve a uniform distribution of structural rigidities and masses. In buildings and structures

made of prefabricated elements, it is recommended to locate joints outside the zone of maximum effort; it is necessary to ensure the uniformity and solidity of structures through the use of reinforced prefabricated elements.

The choice of space-planning schemes, their shape and dimensions has a significant impact on the seismic resistance of buildings. The most preferred forms of structures in the plan are a circle, a polygon, a square and outlines close to them in shape. However, such shapes do not always meet the planning requirements, therefore, a rectangular shape is most often used with parallel spans, without height differences between adjacent spans and without reentrant corners. If there is a need to create complex shapes in terms of the building, then it should be cut along the entire height into separate closed compartments of a simple shape.

The design solutions of the compartments during an earthquake should ensure the independent operation of each of them. This is achieved by the device of anti-seismic seams, which can be combined with temperature or sedimentary seams. Anti-seismic seams are carried out by installing paired walls, paired columns or frames, as well as by erecting a frame and a wall. With a building height of up to 5 m, the width of such a seam should be at least 3 cm. For buildings of greater height, the width of the seam is increased by 2 cm for every 5 m of height.

In multi-storey buildings, an important role in their seismic resistance is played by the structures of interfloor ceilings and coatings, which work as stiffening diaphragms, ensuring the distribution of seismic load between vertical bearing elements. Prefabricated reinforced concrete floors and roofs of buildings must be monolithic, rigid in the horizontal plane and connected to vertical load-bearing structures.

The side faces of panels (plates) of ceilings and coverings must have a keyed or corrugated surface. For connection with an anti-seismic belt or for connection with frame elements in panels (slabs), reinforcement outlets or embedded parts should be provided. The mass of the structure has a significant influence on the values of seismic loads.

Therefore, under the action of seismic forces, it is necessary to strive for the maximum possible reduction in the weight of structures and the resulting loads (fig.1).

Fig.1. Improving seismic resistance of modern buildings

Non-bearing elements such as partitions and frame fillings are recommended to be made light, as a rule, of a large-panel or frame structure and connected to walls, columns, and with a length of more than 3 m - to ceilings. In buildings with more than five floors, the use of hand-made brickwork partitions is not allowed. Partitions made of brick or stone should be reinforced for the entire length at least every 700 mm in height with rods with a total cross section in the seam of at least 0.2 sq. see. It is allowed to carry out suspended partitions with movement limiters from the plane of the panels.

Stone buildings receive the most damage during earthquakes compared to other types of buildings of modern construction.

The seismic resistance of stone buildings is determined by the strength of brick and stone, and also depends on the strength of their adhesion to the mortar. According to current regulations, it is recommended to build load-bearing brick and stone walls, as a rule, from brick or stone panels, blocks manufactured in the factory using vibration, or from brick or stone masonry on mortars with special additives that increase the adhesion of the mortar to brick or stone.

Conclusion.

Accordingly, to ensure seismic resistance, the choice of a construction site is important - proximity to discharge lines should be avoided. Changes are also being made to the foundations of structures - “pillows” are created from concrete or polymeric materials, thanks to which buildings slide or “float” during an earthquake and do not break along those lines where the greatest stress is created.

The most promising direction for improving seismic resistance is the seismic isolation of buildings. Seismic isolation means detuning the frequencies of vibrations of the building from the prevailing frequencies of the impact. This is what ensures the reduction of the mechanical energy received by the structure from the base.

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